

Mixing Livestock in a Forest

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Silvopastoral system established with different types of livestock on forest land in Galicia (NW Spain).

Maximizing the economic return from forest should be based on the understory use for agricultural purposes. Due to the long tradition of agroforestry systems in Europe in the past, the use of livestock in forest as a silvopasture agroforestry practice can be a good solution to increase the deliver of ecosystem services from the forest. Livestock production should be based on the availability of high quality and palatable species in the forest. Understory species are not usually shown in forest lands due to the difficulty to establish commercial grasses that are usually selected to be grown in open sites, that does not perform well under shade conditions. Moreover, the establishment of grasslands as forest understory is usually not carried out due to the difficulty of machinery to plough the land with trees and the possible damage that the machinery may cause to the trees. Therefore, the best option is to analyse the type of plant feed species we have (either woody perennials or grasses) and match the sources with the animal needs. Performing transects or UAV (unnamed aerial vehicles) in forest stand can provide a clear idea of the potential that the understory species have as feed. Usually, tall species such as gorse (*Ulex spp*), (*Rubus spp*) and Fern (*Pteridium spp*) appear in Atlantic regions that are differently consumed by the various autochthonous breeds and species. For example *Ulex* is consumed by goats, autochthonous cows and horses, but *Rubus spp.* is not consumed by horses. Therefore, when a heterogeneous understory composition is found, the best solution is to mix livestock to avoid over and undergrazing and obtain various types of products that increase the resiliency to climate change and market variations linked to the business environment.

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